

Strategy for Modeling Threats in 5G and B5G Networks

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Abstract—The success of the Fifth Generation (5G) cellular network has opened up opportunities for connecting multiple devices and accommodating various different services and applications. However, the architecture of 5G and network functions are susceptible to various cyber-attacks and security risks. Threat modeling facilitates the identification of threats, assessment of potential attacks, and the assessment of applying the mitigation targeting a system. While existing research on 5G threat modeling focuses solely on public network attacks targeting the 5G infrastructure, it is equally important to develop tailored approaches for addressing emerging threats occurring at 5G and B5G infrastructure. Furthermore, current research lacks detailed information on threat vectors, entry points, and network vulnerabilities. To address this gap, this paper proposes a threat modeling strategy specifically designed for characterizing and modeling threats in 5G and B5G networks. The proposed XML schema provides information on vulnerabilities, entry points, attacks, TTPs and correlates countermeasures with the MITRE framework. The proposed approach is exemplified through the illustration of a DNS amplification attack that employs tactics and techniques relevant to telecommunication networks.

Index Terms—Threat modeling, 5G and B5G networks, Meta-model, Domain-specific threat modeling.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Fifth Generation (5G) Mobile Communication Network is the latest 3GPP (Third Generation Partnership Project) standard which ensures ultra-low latency and high bandwidth. Such performance guarantees tremendous benefits and facilitates the deployment of diverse applications and services leveraging virtualization, cloud-based services, edge computing, network slicing and any other emerging technology. However, as with any usual network, 5G architecture is exposed to various cyber-attack and security risks [1], [2]. Threats in 5G networks can arise from multiple sources, including malicious actors, vulnerabilities in enabling technologies, and entry points in network architectures. Utilization of enabling technologies such as software-defined networking (SDN), edge

computing, and/or virtualization introduces new threats and vulnerabilities. Therefore, it is imperative to identify new emerging threats that help us in quantifying and evaluating the network vulnerabilities under various attacks. Different reported vulnerabilities are identified in publicly available databases, as the Common vulnerability exposure (CVE) [3]. This database assigns a unique ID to the reported vulnerability and provides related information such as the attack type, component involved, impact, and attack vector respectively.

Threat Modeling is a structured way of identifying, analyzing, and modeling the cyber-attack at the system, component, and application levels. Traditional threat modeling approaches like STRIDE (spoofing, tampering, repudiation, information disclosure, denial of Service, and elevation of privilege) [4] and CAPEC (Common Attack Pattern Enumeration and Classification) are adopted in 5G networks to analyze the vulnerabilities of the system. However, these approaches are limited to address security controls and characterization of emerging attacks on 5G and Beyond 5th Generation (B5G) including private 5G networks. Private networks, which are utilized by applications such as smart cities, telehealth, and automated industrial processes, are vulnerable to various attacks such as; Denial of Service (DoS) attacks, Man-in-the-middle (MITM) attacks, and DNS spoofing.

The threat modeling process involves the selection of a suitable threat modeling framework and populating it with practical and theoretical data. The MITRE ATT & CK (Adversarial Tactics Techniques, and Common Knowledge) [6] is one of the popular open-source threat Modeling frameworks. However, tactics and techniques provided by MITRE are partially suitable for telecommunication networks. Despite the increasing interest in security aspects in the domains of 5G and B5G, there is a limited number of contributions that focuses on the modeling of cyber-attacks on networks associated with these technologies. This can be attributed to the differences between the mobile network and the enterprise network, as

both networks are characterized by distinct trust and threat models. CONCORDIA is a domain-specific threat modeling framework, introduced for modeling attacks occurring on telecommunication networks [7]. In simple words we can say that CONCORDIA contributes to MITRE by enhancing MITRE ATT & CK with new adversarial tactics and techniques created for telecommunication networks. Therefore, it is imperative to have such a modeling framework for 5G networks that can incorporate the new tactics, emerging threat, interaction of new types of devices, new technologies, support for the vertical industry, and the upcoming generation of mobile networks.

From the latest European Network and Information Security (ENISA) report [8] on November 2023, 310 verified incidents have been reported for Denial-of-service (DoS) attacks. DoS is a serious type of event, making the network services unavailable for the legitimate user. When multiple sources are involved in a DoS attack it shifted towards Distributed Denial-of-service (DDoS) attack. DNS amplification attack is also a kind of DDoS attack, having a focus on targeting the core of network. This type of attack is also responsible for exploiting the vulnerability in the core network functions of 5G such as; Access and Mobility Management Function (AMF), Session Management Function (SMF), and User Plane Function (UPF) of the Core Network (CN). These functions are responsible for providing the essential services to the users.

In this work, we are proposing a generic threat modeling strategy to characterize and model different emerging threats in 5G and B5G along with providing appropriate protective measures to secure the infrastructure. More specifically, we are focused on utilizing the tactics and techniques specifically designed for telecommunication networks. We have elaborated the objective of the threat modeling in 5G based system and assets information involved in 5G and B5G networks. We have also highlighted the steps carried out by the adversary with the example of a DNS amplification attack. We have used this example to validate our proposed threat modeling strategy. Moreover, mitigation of specific attacks is also mapped with MITRE ATT & CK to enable service providers to take earlier preventive/mitigation actions. Thus, the main contribution of this paper can be summarized as follows.

- To model and analyze cyber threats in the context of 5G and B5G networks.
- To characterize assets, threat actors, and Tactics, Techniques, and Procedure (TTP) and analyze the cyber-security vulnerabilities, threats, and impact assessment of the attack and mitigation strategy.
- To propose a threat model and formalize it by defining the corresponding XML schema.
- To validate the threat modeling approach in a 5G-based network.

The structure of this paper is presented as follows. Section 2 reviews existing threat modeling approaches and frameworks. Section 3 proposes a novel threat modeling approach that can be used in any complex scenario to characterize and

model emerging threats. Section 4 presents the threat modeling approach through a case study of DNS amplification attack occurring on 5G infrastructure. Finally, we have conclude the paper with some recommendations and future directions.

II. RELATED WORK

Threat Modeling is a structured approach for identifying, analyzing, and modeling cyber-attacks at the system, component, and application levels. Traditional threat modeling approaches include assets-centric, system-centric, and attack-centric respectively. Assets-centric covers the attack on assets and devices of the targeted system along with identifying the targeted assets and likelihood of attack occurrence. System-centric deals with those cyber-attacks that have a clear target on a software or system [9]. Attack-centric is the most important modeling approach that focuses on evaluating the target of the attacker and attempts to identify possible attack vectors that the adversary group wants to achieve.

For the sake of illustration, a discussion is set on the modeling of threats in 5G public networks, 5G private networks, threats on real-world mobile networks, and the mapping of attack countermeasures with publically available databases. Traditional attack-centric approaches including STRIDE, Attack graph, and MITRE ATT & CK were also used in 5G based system. However these approaches present the system with a pre-defined attack vector and are not tailored according to the communication protocol, network and system adopted in 5G infrastructure [10]. The study presented in [11] focuses on modeling the threats associated with service-based architecture on a 5G core network. The authors have identified different high-level threats to the service-based architecture including the unprotected design flaws and shortcomings with new implementation flaws. They also highlight the need to conduct operator-specific threat modeling to cover the threat related to network architecture, protocol, devices, and potential attack vectors. Moreover the study focuses on threats related to network architecture layers and security concerns in the 5G ecosystem using wireless sensor networks (WSN), with a focus on vulnerabilities and threats on real-world mobile networks. STRIDE threat modeling is used in 5G core slicing architecture [4] to analyze the risks associated with the elements and their potential vulnerabilities. Network slicing allows the network operator to offer a logical section of a network to a client that can be optimized to their individual needs. Although the research primarily focuses on the analysis of risk rather than providing practical implementation and mitigation strategies for the identified threats [12], [13]. Another study presented in [14], considers a layered strategy, to identify and categorize the threats at each layer of the 5G architecture distinctively. The layered approach provides a comprehensive understanding of security risks in 5G, along with considering the different functionalities and components at each layer. This approach also facilitates the identification of enabling technologies affected by the identified threats, information on threats associated with threat actors, entry points, and the impact of the threat categories. By mapping the threat

categories with the associated layers, this study provides a structured framework for analyzing and prioritizing the security requirements and potential vulnerabilities associated with the 5G system.

ENISA has published an extensive report on threats and vulnerabilities associated with the 5G-based networks. This report comprehensively discusses the 5G architecture, use cases, and deployment scenarios, focusing on the threats associated with SDN and NFV [10]. In [15], authors have established a three-dimensional taxonomy for NFV security threats in 5G networks. Although the MITRE ATT & CK works well for known threats, there is a gap in understanding the newly emerging threats to come. Specifically, there is a lack of information on the MITRE ATT & CK framework about how the attackers might target certain technologies within 5G including SDN, Network Function Virtualization (NFV), and Network Slicing (NS). Threat modeling is also linked with the domain-specific framework. Bhadra [16] was the first domain specific framework designed for telecommunication networks. However it is limited to provide the techniques that can be applied to 5G enabling technologies related to SDN, NFV, and slicing. Neither Bhadra nor MITRE ATT & CK include these tactics and techniques in their knowledge base. In article [17], a study was conducted using the MITRE ATT & CK framework to address the attacks occurring in 5G core network and key enabler technologies. The authors considered a proactive approach to detect new adversarial techniques to launch attacks on the 5G infrastructure. Another framework, known as the CONCORDIA mobile threat modeling Framework (CMTMF), characterizes threats based on their phase and stage. This framework employs two stages; one for the device and another for the network. Unlike the MITRE ATT & CK framework, the tactics presented in the CONCORDIA framework are not exclusive. These tactics represent a sequence of steps that occur in the device stage and can also occur in the network stage [7].

Limitation of existing work: Different threat modeling approaches have been utilized in the existing state-of-the-art to characterize 5G network threats. These methodologies encompass STRIDE, Attack graph, and the layered approach. However, they have the following limitations. STRIDE is employed to model six distinct types of threats; however, it is not suitable for 5G networks, communication protocols, and systems. Attack graphs, although utilized, fail to encompass the real-time attacks in private 5G networks and are specifically tailored for public 5G networks. Another investigation adopts a layered approach [14] to model attacks on public 5G networks, yet it neglects to address the attacks on private 5G networks. Furthermore, the aforementioned studies fail to establish a correlation between the identified threats and vulnerabilities and established databases such as the CVE and the MITRE ATT & CK framework. There is a need to define a generic strategy to incorporate 5G and B5G based emerging threats. Moreover, it is also important to have such security control that can be implemented as a countermeasure on 5G and B5G attack scenarios.

III. THREAT MODELING STRATEGY

In this work, we have proposed a generic strategy for modeling threats in 5G-based networks. This strategy can be applied to any network scenario including public, private, and real-world attack scenarios. The purpose of threat modeling is to get an in-depth analysis of threat actor views, intentions, motivation, and behavior, which was needed to model the information of the attack, analyze its impact, and take corrective actions accordingly [18], [19]. Using the information on threat modeling elements we have generated the XML schema to support the modeling process and to take appropriate mitigation actions whenever facing a threat or a security risk. Fig. 1 presents the steps carried out for the building of threat modeling strategy.

Fig. 1. Flow of threat modeling strategy

A. Meta-Model

In existing literature meta models are used for the modeling of threats by providing all the necessary information for representing and evaluating the attacks in different domains. The purpose of the meta-model is to present the security elements in such a way that provides the analysis, assessment of cyber risks and provide a comprehensive view of the system under attack. The Meta model is used to provide security in cyberspace by capturing the relationships between different elements, security, and resilience considerations. In our proposed meta model attacks are characterized providing information on organization assets, threat actor, cyber-attack, threat, vulnerability, and control action respectively. In Fig. 2, we have provided an overview of the proposed meta-model, list elements of the meta-model briefly describing them, and describe their relationships [19], [20]. The details of these elements are presented below.

Threat Actor: In the proposed meta model, a threat actor (internal/external) exploit the vulnerabilities in the system using TTP to manipulate the system or disturb the services. The attacker is responsible for initiating a cyber attack with some intention, campaign, or motive towards the system. For this study, we have defined the threat actor as the entity that uses 'skill-set', 'technical' and other resources to breach or compromise the assets, processes, accounts, sensitive information, etc., of the targeted organization. The threat actor is linked with an attack, vulnerability, or TTP in a many-to-many relationship.

Cyber Attack: Cyber attack element include the information about type, pattern, attack vector and pre-requisite. Moreover, we have also link the cyber attack information with MITRE framework by incorporating the 'ID' and 'Type' information.

Fig. 2. Meta-Model

To perform the cyber attack the threat actor try to identify the weaknesses into the system and exploit vulnerabilities. These vulnerabilities were associated with some unwanted impact on the assets.

The cyber-attacks are linked with the threat actor, TTP, and the impact of attack, as the properties of this element describe the nature of the attack and their possible impact(real/estimated) of the infrastructure. The real impact can be accessed from the infrastructure by monitoring the assets and services affected. In contrast to real impact estimated impact of the attack can be accessed via the attack vector information. It can be access through system parameters, affected components and information of services being affected. Impact of attack can help us in understanding the potential impact of attack along with categorizing and tracking the vulnerabilities.

Vulnerability: Vulnerability is some kind of suspicious activity created to place some flaws and weaknesses into the system. The system can be made vulnerable using multiple sources either at software-level, network-level, and application-level, during configuration or involvement with third-party providers. The meta-model makes use of an attack surface to clearly describe the vulnerability. This attack surface includes information on user equipment, network (RAN, CN, edge, etc.), and service information. The source of the vulnerability is defined by the application/network/user process, there is a need to mention the other properties, such as destination, and timestamp.

Organization Assets: Assets include the components (workstations, DNS servers, handheld devices, etc.) and services (roaming, third-party, cloud, etc.) that the threat actor wants to compromise. The proposed threat modeling processes consider the 'ID' and 'Type' of each respective assets.

Tactics, Technique, and Procedure (TTP): TTP refers to the adversary action or threat actor's method of operation. It can make use of adversary intentions, motives, and campaigns that are used to exploit a victim system or apply to its target. More precisely, tactics, "define the goal of the attacker", while the technique, "it includes the software tool used by the attacker to perform the attack" e.g., IP spoofing, and procedure is the "step-by-step procedure on how to launch the attack". The

information of TTP can be useful for gathering cyber threat information related to patterns of attack, deployed resources, and exploit demonstrations.

Threat: A threat is a harmful action conducted by an internal or external entity to impose or exploit vulnerabilities and have impact on the system assets. To identify the threat the threat actor needs to define the weakness from the state-of-the-art or ENISA threat report. The weaknesses can be defined from the specific use case threat activities, observable pattern, and adversary behaviour.

Control Action: Control actions are the security strategies and the policies that are implemented to support and protect the organization's assets. Preventive actions and policies are implemented to control and mitigate the threat. These actions act as a safeguard to ensure the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of the system. The description of different mitigation and control actions are described below.

Preventive Control: Preventive controls are the policies and actions that are implemented on the occurrence of a particular event. These actions link with the probability of an unexpected event intended to prevent the appropriate actions from violating the policies or risks associated with the third-party providers.

Mitigation controls: are the countermeasures aimed at preventing the tactic used by the attacker. Mitigation includes what to do as a post-action when facing a possible threat.

Corrective Control: Corrective controls are involved in the course of action or risk management designed to react to the detection of an incident to reduce or eliminate the impact or opportunity of an unwanted event to reoccur.

B. Modeling Process: XML Schema

XML Schema Definition (XSD) is the specification used for describing the structure and content of the XML document. It serves as a blueprint for creating well-formed XML documents. In this study we are using an XSD-based modeling strategy to enable the representation of threats and to define the specification of elements, attributes, and data types, making it easier to understand the information of threats and take earlier corrective action. The XML schema defined has as root element the 'ThreatModel' with a unique ID and a sequence

Fig. 3. XML schema for meta-model

of threatModelElement elements, which consist of an ID to uniquely define each model element and a sequence consisting of all the elements in the meta-model, as shown in Fig 3. All the information defined in the Meta-model is represented in the XML schema by their respective XML element. The 'cyber attacks' and 'control action' in the Meta-model are set as mandatory and all the other elements are set as optional to initiate the threat modeling process as shown in Fig 3. Elements are represented as class elements with information of attributes, data types and child elements. XML schema provides the flexibility to add different types of data and apply restrictions on the data. It allows effective communication in heterogeneous systems, integrates security features, and can be used to detect threats in complex systems/networks. Fig 4 present the XML representation of 'CyberAttack'. The types for the XML elements is defined according to the nature of the elements in the meta-model, most XML elements are complex as they contain child elements and the attributes. Moreover, we have also defined the data types of each element and applied restrictions to define the acceptable values for each XML element. Using this strategy, we can model any threat, as well as the different preventive actions and conditions. The proposed schema strategy also provides the flexibility to map the information of mitigation and control action available on the MITRE ATT & CK framework. To see how this schema

Fig. 4. Schema for cyber-attack

strategy helps in the modeling of attacks in 5G and B5G networks, section 4 presents an example of attack scenario that is validated using the proposed XML Schema.

IV. VALIDATION

In this section, we have defined a use case of 5 G network to validate our modeling strategy. The proposed strategy has been applied on a DNS-reflection amplification attack scenario with the help of defining the objective of threat modeling in 5G based network. The model presented above is quite generic to incorporate the emerging threats occurring in 5G infrastructure. The first step in the threat modeling process is to identify the vulnerabilities in the system/ network/application to exploit the resources and disrupt the services. We have used a 5G infrastructure with core functions and designed a network topology using different assets to validate the strategy defined for the threat modeling. Protecting the assets means security goals are met and supported in a way to meet the objective of the 5G and B5G systems. Security goals ensure the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of the system. Moreover, we have also provide the information on how our proposed strategy can be mapped with the threats and preventive actions available on MITRE and CVE. The details for the different steps of the proposed threat modeling strategy are shown in Fig 5. We have illustrated the attack information

Fig. 5. Steps for applying threat modeling strategy

with our modeling process to provide an overview of the attack and available countermeasures by linking it with the publicly available MITRE ATT & CK framework.

A. Objective of TM in 5G

The objective of threat modeling in a 5G based network is to identify and analyze the potential security threats and vulnerabilities to develop effective mitigation and control mechanisms. The overall infrastructure of 5G includes a core network, RAN (radio access network), and various other components like base station, user equipment, and network functions. The purpose here is to identify software, hardware, and network information to design processes and policies.

1) Capturing the approach to achieve the security goals:

This activity defines the action required to achieve the primary goal. The goal of 5G is to revolutionize mobile communication and provide improved performance, speed low latency, and support for a massive number of connected devices. Security

goals in 5G ensure that the 5G network provides a secure and reliable communication service, and provides support to a wide range of applications and use cases in diverse and complex environments.

2) *Capturing the requirements of network topology*: The requirements need to support a variety of services, devices, and applications in 5G and ensure the security goals of confidentiality, integrity, and availability of the system. In this study, we have mentioned a few of the key requirements for the network topology using a 5G environment including core functions, DNS clients, DNS server, tstat, gNB, routers, and topology information of the software to ensure the security concerns and constraints

B. Attack Model using Attacker Steps

The attack model considers the steps carried out by the adversary to deploy the attack. The first step taken by the adversary is to gather data about the 5G infrastructure, assets, vulnerable spots, and other topological information and the selection of TTP on the attack surface. The steps taken by the adversary can be explained by the TTP as; 'Tactics' include information on reconnaissance, 'Techniques' include gathering the data about victim network information (entry points in 5G network) and 'Procedure' includes the information of identifying DNS, query exfiltration data, and steps to deploy the attack. The details of the steps taken by the adversary are mentioned in Fig 6.

Fig. 6. Steps taken by the adversary

1) *Reconnaissance*: To gain knowledge about the infrastructure and targeted assets in a 5 G-based network, the attacker can perform vulnerability scanning and collect information about the victim network. Subsequently, the attacker identifies the vulnerable spot to infiltrate the network. The adversary carries out reconnaissance and information gathering to identify the potential devices. Within the 5G and B5G networks that could be compromised and added to a botnet. The details steps for reconnaissance are mentioned below.

- The attacker can gather the information actively or passively, using IP and vulnerability scanning to get the

victim’s hardware, software, and other operating system resources.

- The attacker can gather Victim network information such as; DNS server, DNS resolver, network topology, IP addresses, domain properties, network security appliances (firewall, IPS, IDS, and other security solutions), and network trust dependencies.
- An adversary can use perimeter mapping of network infrastructure to gather the target information such as DNS enumeration to discover the potential IP address and perform IP and Port scanning.
- After the initial access the attacker can use IP spoofing to remain persistent in case the system restarts or other interruption.
- What type of attack can be initiated using the infrastructure of 5G and B5G networks (DoS attack, DDoS Man-in-the-middle attack, etc.?)

2) *TTPs*: To launch the attack we are using the TTPs used for telecommunication networks. In this work, we are some general tactics from MITRE ATT & CK and others from the specific frameworks. This type of attack mostly targets the DNS server and network time protocol (NTP). The detailed information on tactics is shown in Fig 7. using

Reconnaissance	Initial Access	Persistence	Defense Evasion	Standard Protocol Misuse	Collection	Command & Control	Impact
Active Scanning	Acquire Infrastructure	Spoofed IP Address	Detection of individual Device	IP based Technique	Network Specific Identifier	Application Layer Protocol	Network Denial of Service
Gather Victim Network Information	Compromise Infrastructure				Network Specific Data	Traffic Distribution	DoS against Network
Perimeter Mapping of Network Infrastructure	Attack from UE						DoS against User
	Attack from DNS Server						
	Attack from DNS Resolver						

Legend: MITRE ATT & CK (orange), Shadra (green), CONCORDIA (grey)

Fig. 7. Tactics and techniques available in different modeling frameworks

these tactics the attacker can exploit the vulnerabilities, gain access to the network, manipulate DNS responses, and launch an amplification attack.

3) *Entry points*: The attacker leverage different tactics to exploit vulnerabilities within the 5G networks such as DNS servers, assets, topological information software, and DNS configurations. By exploiting these vulnerabilities the attacker gains entry points in 5G networks, as illustrated in Fig 8. The details of different entry points in 5G infrastructure are mentioned below.

- **Entry Point 1 - gNodeB**: As a gateway between the routers in a 5G network and DNS (Domain Name server) to provide the different services to the user of the network. The attacker can use the open interface from gNodeB to attack the 5G network to disturb the services provided by the DNS. The attacker can also provide inferences to the radio baseband.
- **Entry Point 2- Remote Access**: Different networks allow remote access to the network through the firewall, letting the attacker penetrate the system via a remote source. The threat actor can also gain remote access through third-party providers.

Fig. 8. Network topology of 5G network

- Entry point 3- Botnets: The attacker can use multiple user equipment (UE) or bots to influence the routing of traffic. The attacker can spoof the IP addresses of one of the DNS clients and flood the messages on the DNS server for a specific amount of time. This flooding of messages overwhelms the DNS server and core of the network.
- Entry point 4-UPF: The attacker can target the perimeter of the public land mobile network to influence user plane messages.

4) *Experiment*: : The attacker can use various (TTP) methods and tools to penetrate and gain access to the victim system and identify different vulnerable spots. For example, consider a case of a DNS amplification attack in which the attacker can use a botnet to send a small DNS query to a DNS resolver or he can use the botnet to launch a distributed DDoS attack on a web server by sending a large volume of GET requests. The steps followed for deploying the attack (as shown in Fig 8) can be broken down into the following.

- The attacker can use a botnet to spoof the IP address of the target victim in 5G and B5G network environments by sending a small DNS query to an open DNS resolver.
- The attacker can use a compromised endpoint to send a DNS query with spoofed IP addresses to a DNS resolver. The spoofed address on the packets points to the IP address of the DNS client 4 (IP address: 10.0.27.0/24)
- Each DNS query requests the DNS resolver, with the passing argument of “ANY” to get the response into a large query format.
- When receiving the requests by the DNS resolver it tries to send the larger query response back to the spoofed IP address

C. Impact Assessment

The correlation between the impact of the attack and CVE correlation can be established by utilizing the XML schema elements as shown in Fig 8. To validate our strategy for threat modeling, it is essential to incorporate the necessary details required by the schema element for projecting the impact of attack, specifically the 'system parameters', 'system components' and 'system services'. The system parameters required security considerations such as confidentiality, integrity, and availability. By utilizing the XML schema, we can access the estimated impact of the attack on system parameters,

Fig. 9. XML-example of DNS amplification attack

system components, and system services. For the running example specific vulnerability mentioned in Fig 9 impact of the DNS amplification attack can be represented by the following parameters.

System parameter: Availability of the asset which is being affected. *System Components*: Components that can be impacted by the DNS amplification attack include SDN, NFV, RAN, MEC, cloud server, and core network. Additionally, in the context of service-based architecture, AMF, SMF, and key management servers are also identified as potential targets for DDoS attacks.

System Services: The IP address of the target receives a response along with the surrounding network’s legitimate request-response traffic, resulting in the overwhelming network.

D. Mitigation and Control

Using the proposed threat modeling strategy, we can add the information of 'DNS Reflection-Amplification' attack with the publicly available MITRE ATT & CK framework. The correlation between the information of attack and MITRE can be achieved by utilizing the XML schema elements. To validate the proposed modeling strategy for the specific mentioned attack , we must incorporate respective ID required by ThreatModelElement for each representative attack. For the mentioned DNS amplification attack we have mapped the information of attack with it respective class as cyber attack and correlate the information with MITRE ATT & CK; 'ID' is designated as 'T1498.002' and the 'Type' is defined as "Network Denial of Service: Reflection Amplification". This indicates a correlation between the available attack information on MITRE.

Within our schema, the control actions are categorized into preventive, mitigation, and corrective action plans in response to specific threats. To execute the appropriate action plan outlined by the schema elements, we must provide the information regarding the mitigation action and the corresponding mitigation conditions, which can serve as countermeasures against the threat.

In the example provided above, we have assigned 'ATT & CK IDs' and 'Type' of the mitigation actions to link them to specific tactics, techniques, and procedures outlined in the MITRE framework. This provides us with a standardized way to understand and communicate the nature of the threat

Fig. 10. DNS amplification attack XML

you are mitigating. The particular ID 'ATT & CK IDs' as M1037 indicates a correlation with specific mitigation tactics and techniques. The schema has assigned some mitigation conditions namely 'Type', 'Filter condition' and 'CNF' (true or false). The 'Type' helps in defining the nature of the mitigation condition, 'Filter Condition' define the criteria for the mitigation action to be triggered and CNF, represent the condition either True or False, and determines the activation of mitigation action. If the conditions in the 'Filter Condition' are met, CNF would be true, triggering the mitigation action. In the example mentioned below, we have successfully aligned the attack information and mitigation action available on MITRE with our schema elements, as illustrated in Fig. 10.

CONCLUSION

The role of cyber security is becoming challenging with the integration and interrelationship of multiple interconnected devices to achieve security goals. In this paper, we have analyzed and characterized the emerging threats by managing the elements and their relationship into a meta-model. These elements are then formalized in a generic schema definition to provide a better understanding of the threat information. Meta-models characterize the elements consisting of information on organization assets, threat actors, cyber-attacks, threat, vulnerability, and control action respectively. We have defined an XML schema to enable the representation of cyber threats pre defined in our meta-model. To demonstrate the applicability of our model, we have used the information gathering of adversaries from the threat modeling frameworks using a specific scenario of a DNS amplification attack. The results of the study showed that this modeling approach can improve the modeling process in 5G and B5G systems and provide an earlier course of action to prevent or mitigate them. This work provides a basis for modeling 5G attacks, their impact, and appropriate controlling solutions while using the IDS system and SIEM tools with future networks. In the future, we are planning to consider this threat modeling approach to model the threats occurring in extended reality. We also have a plan to test the generated XML models on earlier assessments of threats and prediction results by integrating them with a digital twin.

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